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Antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activities of secondary metabolites of an endophytic fungus isolated from *Ageratum conyzoides*

Nonye T. Ujam^{1*}, Peter M. Eze², Chidimma R. Chukwunwejim¹, Festus B. C. Okoye³, Charles O. Esimone²

¹ Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State, Nigeria

² Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

³ Department of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

* Correspondence: nonyetreasure@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT: Endophytes have proven to be the promising sources of biologically active products which are of interest for specific medicinal applications. In this study, secondary metabolites of an endophytic fungus isolated from fresh leaves of *Ageratum conyzoides* was investigated for antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties. Isolation of the endophytic fungus, fermentation and extraction of the fungal secondary metabolites were carried out using standard procedures. The extract was evaluated for antimicrobial activity using the agar well diffusion and agar dilution methods. Also, the immunomodulatory activity of the extract was evaluated using cyclophosphamide-induced immunosuppression assay. The crude fungal extract was subjected to High Performance Liquid Chromatography-Diode Array Detector (HPLC-DAD) analysis to identify the chemical constituents. The endophytic fungal extract at 1 mg/ml, exhibited antimicrobial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella Typhi*, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* with inhibition zone diameters of 8, 5, 3 and 2 mm respectively. Also, the minimum inhibitory concentrations of the extract against the test organisms ranged from 0.03-1 mg/ml. The extract at 100 and 200 mg/kg, showed immunostimulatory activity in a dose related manner with a significant increase in the total white blood cells and neutrophil levels. The extract also exhibited immune-protective properties by inhibiting the immunosuppressive activity of cyclophosphamide. HPLC-DAD revealed the presence of xanthorrhizol, orsellinic acid, p-hydroxybenzoic acid, scalarolide reported previously to have antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties. The secondary metabolites of the endophytic fungus isolated from *A. conyzoides* displayed both antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activities.

Keywords: *Ageratum conyzoides*; Endophytic fungus; Antimicrobial activity; Immunomodulatory activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Endophytes are an endosymbiotic group of microorganisms, often bacteria or fungi, that colonize the inter- and/or intracellular locations of plants. All or part of their life cycle, these organisms live within their hosts without causing any apparent symptoms of disease [1, 2]. Endophytes act as reservoirs of bioactive secondary metabolites that serve as a potential source for novel antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer and other biologically important compounds. While plant sources are being extensively explored for new chemical entities for therapeutic purposes, endophytic microbes offer a more promising approach as an important source for drug discovery [3].

Ageratum conyzoides L. (Asteraceae), commonly called goat weed, is an invasive weed found in Nigeria and other parts of the world [4]. The plant is used in traditional medicine to treat dysentery, diarrhea, fever, colic, rheumatism, headache, pneumonia, wounds and burns [5, 6]. *A. conyzoides* has been reported to show antimicrobial, insecticide and nematicide activities [7-10]. This plant had previously been investigated for their endophytic bacterial population, and secondary metabolites expressed by these endophytes have shown a wide range of biological activities [11-14] but the endophytic fungal populations are yet to be explored.

Based on the ethnobotanical history of *A. conyzoides*, the plant was selected for this study with the aim of isolating endophytic fungi from the plant leaves and evaluating the fungal secondary metabolites for antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activities.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Collection of plant materials

Fresh leaves of *A. conyzoides* were collected in July, 2015 from Akegbe-Ugwu, Enugu State, South-East Nigeria. The plant material was identified by a plant taxonomist and a voucher specimen (PCG474/A/020) was deposited in the herbarium of the Department of Pharmacognosy and Traditional Medicine, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

2.2. Isolation of endophytic fungus, fermentation and extraction of secondary metabolites

The isolation of endophytic fungus from the plant leaves, fungal fermentation and extraction of metabolites followed the procedure previously reported [15]. The plant leaves were rinsed gently with running tap water and were cut into small fragments. The leaf fragments were successively surface-sterilized by dipping in 2% sodium hypochlorite for 2 min, 70% ethanol for 2 min, followed by rinsing in sterile water for 5 min, and then dried by blotting in sterilized blotting paper. About 4-6 sterilized leaf fragments were evenly placed in Petri plates containing Malt Extract Agar (MEA) supplemented with chloramphenicol. The plates were incubated at 25-27°C and fungal growths from the leaf fragments were monitored. Hyphal tips were transferred and sub-cultured on MEA plates. This was repeated until pure fungi cultures were obtained. The isolated endophytic fungus was subjected to solid state fermentation in 1L Erlenmeyer flask containing sterilized rice medium (prepared by autoclaving a mixture of 100 g of rice and 100 ml of distilled water). The flask was inoculated with 3 mm diameter agar blocks containing the fungus and incubated at 25-27°C for 21 days. At the completion of fermentation, the fungal secondary metabolites were extracted with ethyl acetate and then concentrated under vacuum at 40°C

2.3. Antimicrobial assay

2.3.1. Preliminary antimicrobial screening

Extracts from endophytic fungi were screened for antimicrobial activity using the method described by Akpotu et al. [16]. The extract was tested against two Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) and three Gram-negative bacteria (*Salmonella Typhi*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and

Pseudomonas aeruginosa), and two test fungi (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*). A concentration of 1 mg/ml of the extract was prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 100% v/v). Standardized inoculums of the test pathogen were aseptically spread onto Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) plates for bacteria and fungi tests respectively. Using a sterile cork borer, 6 mm wells were made in the plates and the fungal extract and controls were put in the wells. Ciprofloxacin (5 µg/ml) and miconazole (50 µg/ml) were used as the positive control in the antibacterial and antifungal assays respectively, while DMSO (100% v/v) was used as the negative control. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h for the test bacteria, and 25°C for 48-72 h for the test fungi. After the incubation, the inhibition zone diameters (IZDs) around each well were measured and recorded in millimeter (mm).

2.3.2. Determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs)

The MICs of the fungal extracts were determined against the test organisms on which the extracts showed activity in the preliminary antimicrobial screening using the agar dilution method described by Akpotu et al. [16]. A stock solution (5 mg/ml) of the fungal extract was prepared in DMSO, and was further diluted in a 2-fold serial dilution to obtain the following concentrations: 2.5, 1.25, 0.625, 0.3125, 0.156, and 0.0781 mg/ml. Agar plates were prepared by pouring 4 ml of molten double strength MHA and SDA (for bacteria and fungi respectively) into sterile Petri plates containing 1 ml of the various dilutions of the extract making the final plate concentrations to become 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125, 0.0625, 0.03125, and 0.0156 mg/ml. Standardized cultures of the test microorganisms were streaked onto the surface of the agar plates containing dilutions of the extract. The MHA plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 h and the SDA plates were incubated at 25°C for 72 h, after which all plates were observed for growth. The minimum dilution (concentration) of the extract, which completely inhibited the growth of each organism, was taken as the MIC.

2.4. Immunomodulatory assay

Evaluation of the immunomodulatory property of the endophytic fungal extract was carried out using the cyclophosphamide-induced immunosuppression method described by Augustine et al. [17], but with modification. Swiss albino mice (25-28 g) were divided into 4 and 2 groups for the curative and the prophylactic studies respectively. Each group contained 5 animals. The animals were allowed unlimited access to food and water *ad libitum* and were placed under standard laboratory animal house condition. The principles of laboratory animal care (NIH publication No. 85-23, revised 1985) were adopted. For the curative study, the mice were induced (suppressed) with 30 mg/kg of cyclophosphamide and afterward treated with 100 and 200 mg/kg of the fungal extract, as well as with the positive and negative controls (NONI and Distilled water respectively). Blood was collected before the induction (basal blood), 3 days after the induction, 5 days after treatment and finally after 10 days treatment and analyzed for hematological parameters. For the prophylactic study, the mice were pre-treated with 200 mg/kg of the fungal extract for 10 days and then induced with 50 mg/kg cyclophosphamide. Blood was collected after 3 days for hematological analysis and the percentage inhibition of cyclophosphamide suppression calculated:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Suppression in control} - \text{Suppression of the treated}}{\text{Suppression in control}} \times 100$$

2.5. High-Performance liquid Chromatography-Diode-Array Detection (HPLC-DAD) analysis

The dried fungal metabolite extract (2 mg) was reconstituted with 2 ml of HPLC grade methanol. The mixture was sonicated for 10 minutes, followed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. Then, 100 µl of the dissolved samples were transferred into HPLC vials containing 500 µl of the HPLC grade methanol. The HPLC-DAD analysis was carried out on the sample with a Dionex P 580 HPLC system coupled to a photodiode array detector (UVD340S, Dionex Softron GmbH, Germering, Germany). Detection was at 235, 254, 280, and 340 nm. The separation column (125 mm × 4 mm; length × internal diameter) was pre-filled

with Eurospher-10 C18 (Knauer, Germany) and a linear gradient of nanopure water (adjusted to pH 2 by addition of formic acid) and methanol was used as eluent. The absorption peaks for the fungal extract was analyzed by comparing with those in the HPLC-ultraviolet (UV)/visible database.

3. RESULTS

An endophytic fungus (code name: ACL4) was isolated from the leaves of *A. conyzoides* (Figure 1). The result of the antimicrobial screening of the fungal extract showed that at the 1 mg/ml, the extract exhibited antibacterial activity only against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhi* (with IZDs of 8 and 5 mm respectively), and antifungal activity against the two test fungi *C. albicans* and *A. niger* (with IZDs of 3 and 2 mm respectively) (Table 1). The MICs of the fungal extract against the two susceptible Gram-negative bacteria *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhi* were 0.0625 and 0.03125 mg/ml respectively. Also, MICs of the extract against the two test fungi *C. albicans* and *A. niger* were 0.5 and 1 mg/ml respectively (Table 2).

Figure 1. *Ageratum conyzoides* and the isolated endophytic fungus (ACL4).

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of the endophytic fungal extract against test organisms (mean IZD in mm).

Test organisms	Endophytic fungal extract (1 mg/ml)	Positive control	Negative control
		Ciprofloxacin (5 µg/ml)	DMSO (100% v/v)
<i>S. aureus</i>	0	6	0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	8	4	0
<i>S. typhi</i>	5	10	0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	0	24	0
<i>B. subtilis</i>	0	8	0
		Miconazole (50 µg/ml)	DMSO (100% v/v)
<i>C. albicans</i>	3	15	0
<i>A. niger</i>	2	8	0

Table 2. MICs of the endophytic fungal extract against test organisms.

MICs (mg/ml)						
<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
-	-	0.03125	0.0625	-	0.5	1

Results of the immunomodulatory assay of fungal extract are presented in Figures 2 and 3. In the curative assay, after the cyclophosphamide-induced suppression, the total white blood cell (WBC) and neutrophil levels of the mice were significantly increased during 5 and 10 days treatment with 100 and 200 mg/ml of the fungal extract (Figures 2 and 3). In the prophylactic study, 200 mg/kg of extract significantly inhibited the cyclophosphamide suppression by 77% (Table 3). The chromatogram of the HPLC-DAD analysis showing bioactive compounds (xanthorrhizol, orsellinic acid, p-hydroxybenzoic acid, scalarolide) present in the extract and the UV spectra of the detected compounds are shown in (Figs. 4 and 5) respectively.

Figure 2. Curative assay: mean total WBC counts 5 and 10 days after administration of 100 and 200 mg/ml of fungal extract (ACL4).

Figure 3. Curative assay: mean percentage neutrophil counts 5 and 10 days after administration of 100 and 200 mg/ml of fungal extract (ACL4).

Table 3. Prophylactic assay: inhibition of immune-suppression by the fungal extract.

Sample	Level of suppression	Inhibition of cyclophosphamide suppression (%)
Distilled water (10 ml/kg)	4.9	0
Fungal extract (200 mg/kg)	1.1	77

Figure 4. HPLC-DAD Chromatogram of extract of the endophytic fungus (ACL4) isolated *Ageratum conyzoides*.

Figure 5. UV Spectra of the different bioactive compounds detected in the extract of endophytic fungus (ACL4) isolated from *Ageratum conyzoides*.

4. DISCUSSION

Endophytes have been known to be a rich source of secondary metabolites with diverse biological properties including antimicrobial [18, 19], antioxidant [20, 21], antitumor/anticancer [22-24], antiviral [25], insecticidal [26, 27] activities, many of which are of great importance to the pharmaceutical and agricultural industries. This group of organisms is a promising source of novel therapeutic molecules that can be explored in drug development for the effective treatment of diseases.

For many generations, extracts of *A. conyzoides* have been used in Nigeria to treat various infections [5, 6]. In this study, the endophytic fungus was isolated from the leaves of *A. conyzoides*. Secondary metabolites of the endophytic fungus were investigated for antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activities. The fungal crude extract demonstrated both antibacterial and antifungal activities (Table 1). Antimicrobial activity of the extract of the endophytic fungus showed significant effect on two of the three Gram negative bacteria and different fungi tested but had no effect on the Gram positive bacteria. Similar result was recorded with extract of endophytic actinomycetes isolated from *A. conyzoides* which showed antimicrobial activity against the tested microorganisms [11].

Immunomodulation includes both stimulation and suppression of the immune system. Cyclophosphamide possesses potent immunosuppressive properties [28] which made it cause a significant drop of white blood cells (WBC) in the test mice. Treatment of the mice with the endophytic fungal extract in the curative assay resulted in an increase in total WBC compared to the negative control groups treated with distilled water. The fungal extract showed significant counteracting effect to cyclophosphamide-induced

reduction in total WBC and neutrophil levels. The extract potentiated the non-specific immune response and could be said to be immunostimulatory in action [29].

The hematological parameter of the mice showed that the endophytic fungal extract displayed a high degree of immune-stimulation by increasing the total WBC and neutrophil counts 5 and 10 days after treatment with the extracts following suppression with cyclophosphamide (Figures 2 and 3). Hematological parameter such as total white blood cells, red blood cells, hemoglobin and neutrophils constitutes the key components of the immune system [30]. A rise and fall in the concentration of these cells stimulates and suppresses the body immune constitution respectively. The extract in addition exhibited immune-protective properties by inhibiting the immune-suppressive activity of cyclophosphamide (Table 3).

The HPLC-DAD analysis revealed that most of the compounds detected are phenolics and It is well established that phenolic compounds are a rich source of valuable potential therapeutic agents for immune system modulation [31, 32]. Immunostimulants enhance the overall immunity of the host, and present a non-specific immune response against the microbial pathogens [33].

Orsellinic acid (2, 4-dihydroxy-6-methylbenzoic acid), a derivative of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid demonstrated antimicrobial activity against a number of microorganisms [34, 35]. Xanthorrhizol (XNT) is a bisabolane-type sesquiterpenoid compound and has been established to possess a variety of biological activities such as anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antihyperglycemic, antihypertensive, antiplatelet, nephroprotective, hepatoprotective, estrogenic and anti-estrogenic effects [36]. *p*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (PHBA) is an organic chemical which can be obtained naturally as well as synthetically. Literature survey reveals its various biological properties which include antimicrobial, antialgal, antimutagenic, antiestrogenic, hypoglycemic, anti-inflammatory, anti-platelet aggregating, nematicidal, antiviral, antioxidant, etc. [35].

The extract of the endophytic fungus isolated from *A. conyzoides* leaves displayed both antimicrobial and immune-stimulatory activities. The presence of antimicrobial and immune-stimulatory compounds in the extract must have contributed in the biological activities demonstrated by the extract.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study shows that the secondary metabolites of the endophytic fungus isolated from *A. conyzoides* possess both antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties and could be potential source new bioactive compounds for drug discovery.

Author Contributions: This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. COE and FBCO designed and supervised the study. NTU and PME managed the laboratory analyses. NTU, PME and CRC managed the data analysis and literature searches, and prepared the first draft of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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